

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

3rd TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Hybridization of thermal and electrical storage simulations using TRNSYS simulation studio and validation from PROTEAS micro-grid data.
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	HySTORE B
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	PROTEAS
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Molten salt storage, battery storage, hybrid storage solutions and modelling.
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	18/03/2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	31/03/2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	19/03/2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	29/03/2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	5 days
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	During the public holidays and weekends the facility was closed
Number of days using the RI	8 days
Number of users granted access (group size)	One person
Comments	I arrived at 18 th late night.
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>During the Christmas break, I worked on integrating all inputs into a unified TRNSYS simulation, finishing the building of the TRNSYS simulation studio model that accurately calculated the total power output. This included methodically creating the simulation to reflect the complex connections and dependence between various components of PROTEAS' smart grid system.</p> <p>During the next week, my efforts were focused on getting real-time operational and meteorological data from the facility's components. I fully gathered information to further evaluate and develop the simulation model, with the goal of establishing a direct link between the simulation outputs and the real-world data being collected. This technique was critical for</p>	

improving the simulation's accuracy and dependability, ensuring that it appropriately reflected the operational dynamics and performance metrics seen at the actual PROTEAS facility.

By closely matching the simulation with real-time data, I hoped to improve its prediction skills and capacity to properly model various operating scenarios. The repeated steps of data collecting and model improvement helped significantly to the simulation's overall efficiency and accessibility for measuring and optimizing the smart grid system's performance.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

My major goal at the PROTEAS facility was to interact with the information collected and show it in a way that allowed for correlations of generated power output to the current weather and environmental conditions. This technique entails combining data from numerous sources to provide insight into how external influences affect electricity generation inside the facility's smart grid configuration.

I plotted the power production of each system and the overall power production to obtain data which I can compare the real output which PROTEAS facility is collecting. I tried also to obtain other useful data like the temperature of the tank, the weather conditions, stage of charge of the batteries and when the electrical heaters are operated.

The first stage is to compile and organize data sets collected from PROTEAS, which include information on solar radiation levels, wind speeds, ambient temperatures, and other meteorological characteristics. By graphing this data against equivalent power output values, we may identify patterns and correlations that reveal information about the system's performance under different environmental circumstances.

Furthermore, I want to perform a detailed review by comparing the power output data generated by the TRNSYS simulation to the real meteorological data used by TRNSYS to create output forecasts. This comparison examination helps to validate the simulation model's correctness and dependability, allowing us to measure its usefulness in replicating real-world circumstances.

The display of these datasets using appropriate graphical representations will allow for more complete visual evaluations. Using these graphical representations, we may identify patterns and correlations between the modelled power output and actual data. This technique provides a foundation for establishing educated assumptions and updating our simulation model to improve its prediction capabilities.

By building a strong link between the simulation model and actual data, we hope to derive ideas that can help think future electricity generation. This predictive capability is crucial for operational planning and grid management, allowing participants to improve energy distribution and allocation in a more efficient and responsive manner.

Furthermore, the capacity to predict future output levels based on environmental conditions enables proactive modifications to grid infrastructure. System operators may use data-driven model inputs to adopt preventive adjustments to handle changes in renewable energy generation, therefore improving system stability and dependability.

In basic terms, the process of data integration, visualization, and analysis performs two functions: it checks the correctness of our simulation model and gives actionable insights for enhancing grid operations. We can encourage a more sustainable and resilient energy environment by iteratively improving our model in response to real-world data.

My involvement with the data at PROTEAS is focused on using the power of information to improve our understanding of renewable energy dynamics within the facility. By crossing the gap between simulation results and real data, we enable informed decision-making and proactive grid management techniques. This effort helps to the development of a more efficient, responsive, and sustainable energy infrastructure.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

By the end of my research, we manage to take the following results:

The power production is following the same curves as the solar radiation and the wind speed.

PROTEAS facility is capable not only to be energy independent but to give also power to the outside grid during the summer months.

The most power production is coming from the inverter PVs and the Stirling Dishes

We can operate all the heaters in the Molten Salt Tank though the hole year and still receive enough power to operate the facility.

The last Plot is showing a prediction for the needed weather data.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The PROTEAS simulation findings are quite encouraging and give reason to be optimistic about the facility's energy production capacity. Based on the results of TRNSYS simulations, PROTEAS has the ability to generate enough electrical power to fulfil its own operational demands throughout the winter months. Furthermore, during the summer months, simulations show that PROTEAS may surpass its internal energy consumption and possibly send excess electricity to the public grid.

However, it is critical to recognize the difference between modelling forecasts and real-world data collected during my time at the facility. The actual power output levels reported during this era were lower than projected, partly owing to the inherent unpredictability of weather patterns and other environmental characteristics that are tough to account for in simulation models.

Moving forward, the convergence of simulation-based forecasts with real-time data observations provides a chance to optimize simulation models and improve predictive accuracy. Future simulations can reflect the dynamic interplay between environmental factors and energy generation dynamics more accurately by including new variables and refining algorithms.

In conclusion, while the simulations provide a promising insight into PROTEAS' energy production potential, the reality of operational problems emphasizes the importance of continual refinement and adaptation. By closing the gap between simulation forecasts and actual results, we may steer towards a more robust and sustainable energy future marked by improved grid performance and operational efficiency.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

I am confident that the simulations I created have tremendous potential for affecting future energy projections and decision-making processes. By incorporating meteorological data into simulation models, we can estimate power production fluctuations in response to dynamic

environmental variables. This capacity is critical for determining the viability of research facilities like PROTEAS becoming industrial-scale power production facilities capable of delivering electricity to the general population.

Furthermore, an important feature of my study is assessing the effectiveness of component connections and control systems inside the PROTEAS infrastructure. Simulation-based evaluations allow us to find possibilities to optimize system settings and improve operational performance. This includes investigating alternate connection options that improve energy production and efficiency while reducing system complexity and resource use.

Finally, the insights gained from these simulations pave the path for strategic improvements in renewable energy integration and grid management. By utilizing simulation-driven evaluations, we can maximize the potential of research facilities such as PROTEAS, transforming them into significant contributors to sustainable energy generation and distribution. Furthermore, improving component connections and control systems based on simulation results promotes ongoing progress and innovation in the field of renewable energy technology.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

PROTEAS facility staff was more than helpful, and they provided me with anything I asked. The only problems I come across was more small errors in the real data which they are expected when you are dealing with real data.

Intended publications

I want to fully finish my research during the summer and write a paper for power simulations and the power smart grid.

Data management

As I mentioned my goal is for a yearly prediction. To achieve that I will have to visit again PROTEAS to collect data though out the whole year.

Conclusions / additional comments

The research is promising good results and a useful output. I really want to finish the project to see what we can get.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
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Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
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Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	<p>Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems.</p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No										
RI extension / upgrades required	<p>In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation.</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No										
Problems with local regulations	<p>Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Health and safety issues	<p>Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details.</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details.</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details.</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details.</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										

Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
Universities in general will help a lot I believe.											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
To achieve high TRL level we must increase the number of research happening in the thermal and mechanical energy storage systems.											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										

Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.